

High-frequency Titration Cells. Part II. Diameter of the Cell

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The role of the diameter of the cell for optimum performance in high frequency titration at 6.47 megacycles has been investigated. Results obtained show that there is a minimum diameter of optimum performance, above which situation does not improve.

The use of high-frequency oscillator received careful attention by the scientists for titration and chemical analysis during recent times¹. In order to obtain a good response during titration, it is necessary to work out the geometrical conditions² of the cell. In our laboratory we have used a capacity type high-frequency apparatus working at 6.47 megacycles. The cell used in this case was a beaker of borosilicate glass with walls 2.3 mm thick and with two electrodes made of copper ribbons, each 1 cm in breadth, wound round the beaker and connected in parallel with other capacitors in the circuit. The distance between the electrodes could be altered when necessary by means of screws fitted to them. In our previous communication³ we reported the influence of the interelectrode distance in high-frequency titrations. In the cells where the electrodes are connected across the walls of the beaker, the electrode distance and the diameter of the cell become identical and consequently the question of studying separately the influence of the diameter of the cell does not arise. But in our apparatus these two quantities being independent of each other, it became necessary to study the effect of the cell diameter during the titration. As the existing literature did not help us very much regarding this point, the study of the cell diameter was considered desirable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experiments were performed with seven cells (prepared locally) of borosilicate glass having different diameters. Care was taken to keep the wall thickness equal in every case during the preparation of the cell. The cells of the following diameters were tried: 1.7, 2.2, 2.6, 3.9, 4.5, 5.0 cm. With each cell titrations were repeated at different electrode distances (Fig. 1).

Titration used in this case was that of a dilute HCl solution (0.00125*N*) with an alkali (0.025*N*-NaOH). For each cell a minimum electrode distance for best performance was

1. Jensen and Parrack, *Anal. Chem.*, 1946, 18, 595.
2. Delahey, "New Instrumental Methods in Electrochemistry"
3. This *Journal*, 1963, 40, 643.

found to be approximately equal to 3.5 cm.³ As evident from Fig. 1, the value of this minimum electrode distance appeared to remain almost constant for each cell. With cells having smaller diameters, the performances were found rather poor and unreliable. On gradually increasing the diameters, the performance of the cell gradually improved till a limiting value was reached, beyond which there was no further improvement. Changes in response in the titration with change in diameters of the cell have been shown in Fig. 2. A good titration curve under the most favourable conditions is shown in Fig. 1. of our previous communication³.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

It appears from Fig. 2 that there is a minimum diameter below which the response will be poor. This value of the diameter comes out to be slightly above 4 cm. Thus to obtain a satisfactory response during titration, working out at first a suitable geometry of the cell is essential. At 6.47 megacycles, following values of the cell geometry have been found to be most reliable: electrode distance = 3.5 cm; diameter of the cell = 4 cm; thickness of the walls = 2.3 mm.

Titration was thus repeated with one of the cells, considered best from our observations with different concentrations of HCl. In every case, the strength of the alkali (NaOH) added from the burette was kept at least ten times stronger than that of the HCl solution kept in the beaker. It was found that the HCl solutions of strengths within the range $N/200$ to $N/1500$ could be titrated satisfactorily. The solutions beyond this concentration range did not respond effectively by yielding a sharp break in the titration curve at 6.47 megacycles.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 evidently shows that the minimum electrode separation to obtain an optimum result is in a way independent of the diameter of the cell. With smaller diameter, the

breaks in the titration curves are not sharp, but with larger diameter the break is sharp and unequivocal up to a certain optimum value, beyond which the titration does not impose with further increase in diameter. Thus with 4.5 cm and 5 cm diameters, the curves almost overlap with each other.

Fig. 2, which is derived from Fig. 1, however, shows almost an S-shaped curve. The increase of diameter increases capacity changes at the end point. Beyond a value of 2.2 cm, the rate of increase jumps and beyond 4.5 cm, the increase reaches a maximum value and the curve presents an S-shaped appearance. Hence at the frequency of the instrument as used by us (viz., 6.47 megacycles/sec.), there is no point in increasing the diameter of the titration vessel beyond 4.5 cm. As to how far changes in frequency may alter this value of the diameter for optimum result will be our next point of investigation.

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Errata

Page.	Line.	Read.	for.
169	Structure (E) to be read as		
212	Ref. No. 3	<i>techeanol.</i>	<i>techeol.</i>
221	Title	Imide	Acid
564	Structure I	Linking between C atoms	
595	Table I Col. 3, line 6	OAc	G
	8	G	OAc
	last column	110-15°	110-18°
622	Eq. (1)	$1/\bar{P}$	$1/p$
623	13	R_p	R_s
	15	P_o	$\bar{P}_o$
625	Table II		
	last column, line 1	0.81×10^{-5}	0.81×10^6
	last line	4.36	4.36

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